

Insights into Academic Output of Universities of Applied Sciences using Linked Open Data

Thiago Albrecht Salviano

Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Twente

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Client: Saxion Ambient Intelligence

*Supervisor: Faizan Ahmed *

*Critical Observer: Marcus Gerhold *

Abstract— Universities of Applied Sciences (UAS) increasingly contribute to applied research and innovation, yet their scholarly outputs and collaborations are challenging to evaluate due to the fact that project, funding, and publication data are dispersed throughout various sources and often lack consistent identifiers. This article describes a Linked Open Data pipeline that combines (i) OpenAlex publication metadata and (ii) NWO/SIA project data that is exposed as RDF to create a project-centric research knowledge graph. The pipeline retrieves open-access PDFs, and uses a large language model to extract grant identifiers from full texts in order to link projects to publications. Starting from 52,640 UAS-affiliated publications in OpenAlex, 557 could be linked to a project record (1.1% of the total), indicating considerable coverage limitations even under "open" conditions. The pipeline demonstrates that linking projects to outputs via funding acknowledgements depends on the availability of open full texts and on consistent reporting of grant identifiers in publications. Although open scholarly graphs make it easier to find and analyse research on a large scale, they may underrepresent UAS research when outputs occur outside conventional publication infrastructures or when funding metadata is inconsistent. This article explains why grant-identifier-based linking by itself might not be enough for institutional research analysis and provides a reproducible method for linking publications and outputs. It also motivates broader strategies that combine open scholarly graphs with additional output sources and richer research metadata to support more representative institutional insight.

1. Introduction

Universities of Applied Sciences (UAS) have increasingly expanded their research activities and institutionalised practice-oriented research, strengthening their role within regional knowledge ecosystems[1]. The nature of research conducted by UAS is applied oriented and practice based, and is closely connected to education and professional practice [2]. Tracking the developments and output in UAS research can be challenging because data is scattered and metadata varies between project descriptions, scholarly publications, funding records, and other forms of non-standard output (e.g., professional reports, tools, prototypes, educational materials), which are more common in UAS contexts [3]. Linked Open Data (LOD) approaches, typically implemented

in the form of knowledge graphs (KGs) offers a potential solution to connect these scattered and heterogeneous data through shared entities and relations (projects, people, organisations, funders), defined according to a common ontology, leading to a single structure that supports logic-based querying and inference, allowing for better analyses of research activity, such as identifying collaboration networks, mapping research trends, tracking funding influence, and assessing institutional performance and impact [4]. Large scholarly KGs and infrastructures (e.g., OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, and OpenCitations) demonstrate the value of unified graphs for discovery, trend analysis, and linkage to persistent identifier registries such as ORCID and DOI [5–8]. In the Dutch context, publicly listed funded projects at the Dutch Research Council (NWO) highlight a rich corpus of research activities; however, relevant funded projects also exist across other governmental, European, and regional funding programmes (e.g., TechForFuture), and meaningful analysis of UAS productivity and collaboration requires that these project records are integrated with publication and citation graphs, researcher/ authors persistent identifiers (i.e. ORCID), and (academic) institution data (e.g. Wikidata), rather than treated as isolated silos [6, 9].

1.1. Problem and Motivation

Institutions like Saxion lack consolidated insights into their scholarly contributions and collaborations, despite an increase in research output.

Analysis is hindered by the fact that project, publication, and funding data are scattered across several sources and sometimes have inconsistent metadata.

This challenge aligns with broader calls to make research information open and interoperable. The Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information argues that openness of research information (particularly research metadata) should become the new norm, in order to support transparent, auditable, and responsible decision making in science and research assessment [10].

1.2. Approach

This article describes a Linked Open Data knowledge graph constructed from heterogeneous sources to analyse research productivity and collaboration at Universities of Applied Sciences. The graph uses a project-centric ontology to represent UAS research activities in a unified semantic structure. In addition to structured data sources, funding information is automatically extracted from full-text publications using a large language model (LLM).

Section 2 reviews graph data models, research-information ontologies, and identifier-based linking. Section 3 describes data collection, document processing, LLM-based information extraction, and knowledge-graph construction. Section 4 presents the datasets and linkage outcomes. Section 5 examines the implications and limitations of the approach and identifies opportunities for improving research visibility at UAS institutions. Section 6 presents conclusions and future research directions.

The knowledge graph is implemented using standard Semantic Web technologies, namely the Resource Description Framework (RDF), which is a standard model for data interchange on the Web, designed to represent information in a machine-readable and semantically rich way. RDF expresses data as a collection of triples, each consisting of a subject, predicate, and object. These triples form statements such as “a publication *is AuthoredBy* a researcher”, thereby describing relationships between entities. Each element in a triple is identified by a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI), which ensures that concepts and entities can be unambiguously referenced across different datasets [11]. This graph representation allows data from multiple sources to be linked, queried, and reasoned over, and is a foundational structure for knowledge graphs and Linked Data applications. For this project, the integrated data is stored in an RDF triple store, containing triples derived from

the prepared datasets.

2. Background Research

2.1. Graph data models for research information

When integrating diverse research data (projects, publications, organisations, funders, and individuals), the first conceptual decision is which underlying data model to use to represent entities and relations. Among the viable options are fixed-schema databases (e.g., relational or document-oriented models), property graphs, and RDF-based knowledge graphs.

RDF uses triples to represent information and enables semantic interoperability by using shared ontologies. This supports explicit meaning modelling and cross-dataset linking using URIs. Unlike fixed-schema databases, RDF operates under an open-world assumption: the absence of a statement does not imply its falsity, and new entities or relations can be added without schema modification. RDF is well-suited to integration scenarios where metadata is incomplete or originates from heterogeneous sources.

Property graphs (as used in many graph database systems) have gained attention for applications that focus on traversal-based analytics, flexible attribute storage, and advanced inference. In property graphs, entities and relationships can directly carry arbitrary properties, which can make certain analytics and application development straightforward. However, property graphs do not inherently rely on globally shared semantics in the same way as RDF, and property graphs usually require local conventions for labels and relationship types.

Finally, a fixed-schema database (e.g., relational tables or a strictly defined document schema) can be an effective alternative when the scope of data is stable and the main goal is operational reporting. A fixed schema can simplify implementation and enforce consistency, but it also makes it harder to integrate additional datasets with different structures, or to represent incomplete and evolving/changing metadata without repeated schema redesign.

Given that this project aims to integrate heterogeneous open research information, reuse established research-information vocabularies, and enable semantic linking to external identifiers (e.g., ORCID, DOI, Wikidata), an RDF-based approach provides the most appropriate foundation for achieving interoperability and extensibility within a Linked Open Data environment, and aligns with widely adopted Semantic Web standards.

2.2. Ontology models for representing projects and research information

Since the European Research Information Ontology (EURIO) was created by the EU Publications Office specifically to publish project information from EU framework programmes as linked data, with classes for projects, organisations, people, funding schemes, and grants that mirror how funded projects are actually recorded and reported [12], it provides a strong foundation for project-centric data (such as data about UAS research projects), which often has to integrate project metadata, organisations, roles, funding schemes, and link to outputs. A recent study, for example, demonstrates that this ontology facilitates project-level analytics and cross-organisation comparisons in a European context by implementing collaborator-recommendation agents directly over a EURIO knowledge graph [13].

The EURIO ontology is compatible with other, adjacent vocabularies (such as DINGO [14] and FRAPO [15]) and can be mapped where necessary [12]. This means that when integration with other systems is needed, adopting EURIO enables alignment with other research-information standards

rather than isolating the resulting data model. If you ingest data from Current Research Information Systems (CRIS), which are information systems used by research organisations to track and manage data on research activities, the long-standing CERIF (Common European Research Information Format) model remains relevant, as its semantic vocabulary and role/type system are widely recognised in research information management [16]. Hence, maintaining a minimal mapping (projects, persons, organisations, roles) preserves compatibility without importing CERIF’s full complexity [16]. Likewise, EURIO’s project/funding pattern is consistent with how the OpenAIRE Research Graph structures “Projects funded by a Funding Stream of a Funder,” which eases future linking to OpenAIRE’s public graph of projects, organisations and results [6]. Finally, recent case studies such as ScienceON show how a project-centred ontology can be applied in a complete system that gathers research information from many sources, checks the consistency of the data, and makes it searchable for analyses such as collaboration mapping and output tracking [17].

2.3. Linking and canonicalisation through identifiers and external knowledge bases

A practical challenge in integrating heterogeneous research data is the consistent identification of entities such as authors, organisations, and projects across datasets that differ in naming conventions as well as in metadata coverage, quality, and granularity. In the context of open scholarly infrastructures, persistent identifiers can partially address this challenge. For example, DOI can serve as a stable identifier for publications, ORCID can identify researchers, and organisation registries such as the Research Organization Registry (ROR) can support institutional canonicalisation. However, coverage is not complete and many records still rely on name strings, local identifiers, or inconsistent naming.

In applied-research contexts such as Dutch UAS institutions, multilingual naming and incomplete affiliation metadata can further complicate linking (e.g., “Saxion University of Applied Sciences” and “Hogeschool Saxion” refer to the same institution, but in different languages). In such cases, external knowledge bases such as Wikidata can support canonicalisation because they store multiple aliases for organisations and connect them to other identifiers. This means that even without implementing full-scale entity-resolution evaluation, it is still possible to improve coherence by reusing external identifier registries and mapping local labels to shared identifiers where available.

3. Methodology

This project follows an iterative methodology for constructing and analysing a research knowledge graph. The approach combines (i) ingestion of structured open research information from heterogeneous sources, and (ii) extraction of additional project- and funding-related metadata from unstructured documents (PDF publications). The resulting data is modelled using the EURIO project-centric ontology and integrated into a triple-store-backed knowledge graph that supports semantic querying.

Two main datasets are produced and connected in this work. The first is a ‘projects’ dataset, exposed as an RDF endpoint, containing projects scraped from the NWO/SIA websites (containing project names, funding amounts, dates, etc.) The second is a dataset derived from PDF processing, containing publication metadata and extracted grant numbers. These datasets are linked based on the grant number, which is used as the project identifier for linking publications to project records.

3.1. Data sources and scope

The work focuses on Dutch Universities of Applied Sciences as the primary scope of analysis, while relying on open standards to remain generalisable beyond this context. Publication metadata is retrieved from OpenAlex by filtering for works affiliated with Dutch Universities of Applied Sciences and the presence of a PDF in the record. Project data is collected by scraping publicly listed NWO/SIA project pages and exposing the resulting dataset through an RDF endpoint.

3.2. Schema and data model

The European Research Information Ontology (EURIO) is adopted as the primary data model for representing research projects, organisations, persons, funding schemes, grants, and their relations. EURIO is chosen because it provides a project-centric schema aligned with how funded activities are recorded, and because it supports integration with adjacent research information vocabularies where necessary. Where project, funding, or output information cannot be represented directly using EURIO alone, complementary vocabularies are used in a minimal way to avoid schema bloat while preserving interoperability.

3.3. Data ingestion and document processing

Data ingestion is performed through scripted pipelines and bulk data acquisition, depending on source availability. Publication metadata is collected from the OpenAlex API, after which a download queue is constructed by selecting a PDF URL when available. PDFs are then fetched from their source URLs using a simple HTTP retrieval approach, and downloads are validated by checking content type before saving.

Downloaded PDFs are converted into a text-based representation (Markdown) for LLM input using the *PyMuPDF4LLM*: a Python library designed to convert PDF documents into Markdown format, specifically optimised for LLM applications. To control processing costs and honour the model's context window size limit, documents above a fixed character threshold are excluded from the LLM extraction stage.

3.4. Grant number extraction with an LLM

Grant numbers and related funding/project signals are extracted from the Markdown-parsed publication text using a structured LLM pipeline. The model used is Qwen3-235B-A22B-Instruct-2507, an open-weight large language model. It is selected primarily for price-to-performance considerations and because it performs competitively on long-context and instruction-following benchmarks [18, 19]. The extraction task is implemented using a schema-constrained output format: the model is constrained to output a complete JSON object that conforms to a predefined JSON schema with the fields `fundingOrgAgency`, `projectName`, `grantNumber`, and `resultType`. Unavailable fields are to be explicitly set to `null`.

The system prompt instructs the model to extract only factual information stated in the paper (typically from acknowledgements or funding statements), to avoid inference/guessing, and to preserve identifiers as written. Post-processing is applied to normalise extracted grant numbers for matching against project identifiers. In particular, a heuristic normalisation step lowercases the extracted value and removes spacing, hyphens, dots, and non-ASCII characters, producing a canonicalised form that is compatible with how grant identifiers appear in the scraped project dataset.

The landscape of LLMs changes rapidly; therefore, the extraction pipeline is designed such that the underlying model can be replaced with other current or future instruction-following models,

provided they can produce structured outputs (i.e. constrained by a schema).

Figure 1. High-level workflow of the publication ingestion and LLM-based metadata extraction pipeline.

3.5. Knowledge graph construction and storage

After ingestion and extraction, the integrated datasets are represented according to the adopted ontology. The resulting triples are loaded into an Apache Jena triple store, enabling semantic querying using SPARQL. Provenance is retained where possible by recording the source of each integrated statement (e.g., the originating dataset or the originating publication from which a funding mention is extracted), allowing the graph to be inspected and refined iteratively.

3.6. Query design and analysis

Analytical queries, implemented in SPARQL (the standard query language for RDF-based knowledge graphs) are defined to support the central goal of providing insights into UAS research productivity and collaboration. Query design focuses on retrieving project–output relations and their associated metadata based on the shared grant identifier. These queries are used to produce descriptive statistics and example use cases that demonstrate how integrated open research information can be explored through the graph.

3.7. Data quality checks

Because the integrated data originates from heterogeneous and partially incomplete sources, quality checks focus on internal consistency and coverage rather than ground-truth validation. Examples of applied checks include coverage rates across pipeline stages (e.g., availability of OpenAlex PDF links, successful PDF downloads, successful grant-number extraction), and basic provenance completeness (whether key entities and relations can be traced to a source). These indicators support iterative refinement of ingestion and extraction steps.

4. Results

4.1. Datasets and linkage strategy

Two datasets are produced and analysed in this work. The first is a projects dataset, exposed through an RDF endpoint, containing projects scraped from the NWO/SIA websites. The second is a dataset resulting from PDF-based extraction, containing publication records and extracted grant numbers. These datasets are linked through the grant number, which serves as the project identifier in the linkage process.

Linking between the datasets uses direct matching on the extracted grant number (i.e., a simple string-based match). No similarity-based matching or additional disambiguation heuristics are applied beyond this direct matching.

4.2. Publication coverage and PDF acquisition

At the time of the research (late January 2026), OpenAlex contained 52,640 publications relevant to the scope of this study. Of these, 29,130 were marked as open access (55.4% of all publications). Among the open access subset, 19,780 publications had a PDF link available in OpenAlex (67.9% of open access publications).

Using a simple approach of fetching PDFs directly from their source URLs, 8,990 PDFs were successfully downloaded (45.5% of publications with a linked PDF). The remaining downloads failed for a variety of practical reasons, most commonly firewall blocks or bot challenges, incorrect file formats or redirects (e.g., links pointing to a landing page rather than a raw PDF), and 404 errors.

Figure 2. Pipeline overview from OpenAlex publication set to successfully linked publications and projects.

4.3. Grant number extraction from PDFs

From the 8,990 successfully downloaded PDFs, the LLM extracted grant numbers from 3,219 documents (35.8%). For 5,767 PDFs, no grant number was extracted, either because the publication

did not contain one (e.g., no explicit funding acknowledgement) or because it was not detected during extraction.

This indicates that, even within the successfully downloaded subset, explicit grant identifiers are present (or recoverable) only for a minority of documents, which constrains the achievable linkage coverage when the grant number is used as the primary join key.

4.4. Project–publication linking results

After matching extracted grant numbers against the projects dataset, 557 publications were linked to a project record. Since projects can have multiple publications, this represents 557 linked publication records rather than 557 unique projects.

Relative to the PDF subset, the linked publications correspond to 6.2% of downloaded PDFs (557 / 8,990). Relative to the subset where a grant number was extracted, 17.3% of publications with extracted grant numbers matched a project record (557 / 3,219). Relative to the total OpenAlex publication set, the linked subset is 1.1% (557 / 52,640).

4.5. Interpretation and limitations of the results

The resulting linked subset is small, which limits the extent to which the current pipeline alone can provide consolidated insights into research output and collaboration. Importantly, the low number of matches does not necessarily imply the approach is incorrect, but it highlights compounding coverage constraints: many publications do not have accessible PDFs; many PDFs do not contain (or do not yield) a grant number; and only a subset of extracted grant numbers correspond to records in the scraped projects dataset.

Furthermore, the linking strategy is fairly conservative: since no similarity-based matching is used, only publications that explicitly contain a grant number that directly matches a project identifier in the projects dataset are linked. This increases precision of matches in practice, but reduces recall and overall coverage.

Finally, the current results only reflect outputs discoverable through OpenAlex and open-access PDF availability, and do not consider additional sources of project outputs (e.g., publications not indexed in OpenAlex, outputs hosted on organisational or company websites, project pages, or other repositories). These sources may contain additional relevant evidence for project–output linkage, but are outside the scope of the present results and remain potential future work.

5. Discussion

5.1. What the results do and do not show

This work demonstrates a practical end-to-end pipeline for linking a project dataset (scraped NWO/SIA projects exposed as RDF) with scholarly outputs collected from OpenAlex, using grant numbers extracted from publication PDFs as the join key. The resulting linked subset is small relative to the initial publication corpus, but it is non-zero and traceable: every match is grounded in an explicit identifier present in the publication text and a corresponding identifier in the project dataset.

At the same time, the current results primarily illustrate a coverage challenge rather than a definitive picture of institutional research output. Even when publication metadata is available at scale, access to full texts is constrained (e.g., broken links, access barriers, and non-PDF landing pages), and explicit grant identifiers are absent (or not reliably extractable) in a large portion of

documents. In other words, the pipeline reveals that the feasibility of project–output linkage via funding acknowledgements depends heavily on availability of open full texts and on consistent reporting of grant identifiers in publications.

5.2. Implications for UAS research visibility and impact insights

Universities of Applied Sciences often aim to demonstrate societal relevance and regional impact, but the evidence base for evaluation is fragmented and not always captured in standardised scholarly channels. Prior work on UAS research impact evaluation highlights that UAS research outputs and impacts are heterogeneous and that evaluation frameworks must account for context and process rather than relying exclusively on traditional bibliometric traces [2]. In that light, the current pipeline can be seen as a narrow but useful building block: it supports one specific type of traceability (project identifier → publication), but it does not yet capture many other forms of UAS output (e.g., professional artefacts, reports, software, prototypes, stakeholder-oriented dissemination).

This also suggests a methodological tension: open scholarly graphs are valuable for discovery and large-scale analysis, but they risk systematically underrepresenting UAS work when outputs occur outside conventional publication infrastructure or when funding information is not consistently encoded.

5.3. Limitations

Several limitations constrain interpretability and scalability.

(1) Source coverage and selection bias. The publication corpus is derived from OpenAlex and further constrained to records with linked PDFs and successful downloads. This introduces a selection effect toward open-access materials and sources that allow automated retrieval.

(2) Reliance on explicit grant identifiers. The linkage strategy requires grant numbers to be explicitly present in the PDF text and extractable by the LLM. Publications that acknowledge funding without identifiers, use informal shorthand, or mention only programme names cannot be linked with the current approach.

(3) Conservative matching strategy. Project–publication links are created through direct matching on a normalised string form of the extracted grant number. No similarity matching, fuzzy matching, or broader entity-resolution methods are applied. This reduces the risk of spurious matches, but it likely lowers recall substantially.

(4) No external validation of extraction accuracy. Although the extraction is schema-constrained and designed to avoid inference, the present results do not include a measured precision/recall evaluation of extracted grant numbers, and therefore the extraction stage is treated as a pragmatic enrichment step rather than a validated information extraction system.

5.4. Future work

The results point to several straightforward directions for improvement.

(1) Expand beyond OpenAlex-linked PDFs. To reduce selection bias and increase coverage, future work can incorporate additional discovery and retrieval routes for full texts (e.g., institutional repositories, publisher APIs where allowed, or alternative open indexes).

(2) Add additional join signals beyond grant number. Complementary linkage evidence could include project titles or acronyms, funder and programme names, and affiliations in the acknowledgements section, combined with controlled heuristics or human-in-the-loop review for ambiguous cases.

(3) Incorporate other UAS output channels. Since UAS outputs are often not limited to journal papers, future work should extend the graph to include non-traditional outputs (e.g., reports, tools, prototypes, professional publications) and evaluate how these can be systematically represented and queried. This aligns with earlier observations that UAS impact evaluation must incorporate context and stakeholder-oriented outputs.

(4) Evaluate extraction and linking quality. A small manually verified subset would enable a measured assessment of extraction quality and match reliability, providing a clearer basis for claims about accuracy and usefulness.

(5) Quality assessment and validation of RDF data. Future work can validate the generated RDF graph using SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language). SHACL defines structural and semantic constraints over RDF data, validating class membership, property usage, cardinalities, and datatype constraints. SHACL-based validation detects inconsistencies automatically and enforces data quality standards across the knowledge graph.

(6) Enhanced provenance modelling using RDF-star. The current implementation records basic provenance metadata. RDF-star (RDF^{*}) attaches metadata directly to individual triples, enabling statement-level provenance. This supports finer-grained tracking of extraction confidence, source documents, and transformation steps, which improves traceability for auditing and graph refinement.

6. Conclusion

This article investigates how a knowledge graph can be constructed from heterogeneous open sources to provide insights into research productivity and collaboration for Universities of Applied Sciences. The main contribution is an implemented, reproducible pipeline that (i) collects publication metadata at scale, (ii) retrieves and parses open-access PDFs where available, (iii) extracts grant identifiers using a schema-constrained LLM pipeline, and (iv) links extracted identifiers to a project dataset exposed as RDF. The resulting linked subset demonstrates that grant numbers can function as a viable join key for connecting project records to scholarly outputs when identifiers are explicitly stated.

However, the results also show that this approach alone provides limited coverage: many publications lack retrievable PDFs, many documents do not contain explicit grant identifiers, and conservative matching further reduces the number of links. Consequently, while the pipeline provides a concrete step toward traceable project–output integration, it is not yet sufficient on its own to offer comprehensive institutional insights. In the context of UAS research, where outputs and impacts are diverse and often not fully reflected in standard scholarly channels, a broader strategy is required that combines open scholarly graphs with additional output sources and richer research metadata.

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Note on AI usage

Throughout this project, the following generative AI tools were used to assist with work: (i) *GitHub Copilot* for coding assistance (code generation and autocomplete); (ii) *Perplexity* for searching through academic literature. All code output from GitHub Copilot was thoroughly reviewed and edited. No generative AI tools were used to write the text of this article.

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Appendix A

The following is the *system prompt* used for guiding the LLM on the information extraction task. The prompt contains some additional context for recurring terms specific to the Dutch research landscape, including English equivalents to Dutch terms and organisation names, so as to help the model correctly recognise project and funding information.

Your task is to read the markdown-parsed content of a scholarly paper and output a **complete, structured JSON object** describing the publication's related project and funding (if any).

Follow these principles:

- Extract only factual information present in the paper.**
 - * Do not infer or fabricate missing data.
 - * If something cannot be found, set its value to `null`.
 - * If you are unsure about a value, use `null` rather than guessing.
- Identify project and funding information.**
 - * From acknowledgements or funding statements, extract:
 - * `projectName`: The names or codes of grants or projects.
 - * `fundingOrgAgency`: The funding programme, organisation/agency, or scheme names (e.g. "Horizon 2020", "NWA").
 - * `grantNumber`: Any grant or project identifiers, numbers, or acronyms.
 - * `resultType`: The type of of research output.
 - * If multiple funders or grants are mentioned, include all of them.
- Consistency.**
 - * When extracting complex fields like project names or funding details, prefer the version as written (verbatim text).
 - * Preserve identifiers (e.g., "GA-123456", "H2020-MSCA-IF-2020") exactly as they appear.
 - * Avoid verbose information, prefer minimal, short identifiers (e.g. for a `grantNumber`, only output the number/id; for affiliation, output the full, unambiguous name of the institution, but avoid adding its full address)
- Glossary**

Below are some context-specific terms that might be relevant for parsing the documents:

- * **Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek (NWO)**: Dutch Research Council - the national research council of the Netherlands. NWO funds thousands of top researchers at universities and institutes and steers the course of Dutch science by means of subsidies and research programmes.

NWO Financieringslijnen | Financing lines (in Dutch):

1. Open Competitie - Nieuwsgierigheidsgedreven onderzoek

2. Talentprogramma - Nieuwsgierigheidsgedreven ongebonden onderzoek gericht op onderzoekstalent
3. Kennis- en Innovatieconvenant (KIC) - Projecten of programma's in samenwerking met externe publieke en/of private partijen
4. Nationale Wetenschapsagenda (NWA) - Bevorderen dat wetenschap bijdraagt aan maatschappelijke en economische uitdagingen
5. Wetenschappelijke infrastructuur - Realiseren van grootschalige infrastructuur

Your final output must represent all the identifiable bibliographic and funding information in structured form, with every field included and unfilled ones explicitly marked as `null`.

Appendix B

Below are three examples of SPARQL queries created to analyse the resulting dataset(s). Note that there are two SPARQL endpoints for these queries: the (local) dataset containing projects, and another dataset containing the publications the LLM-extracted funding information, which is queried, which is queried as a remote SPARQL endpoint through a SERVICE clause:

1. Get 100 projects with dates + identifier

PREFIX eurio: <http://data.europa.eu/s66#>

```
SELECT ?project ?title ?startDate ?endDate ?identifier
WHERE {
  ?project a eurio:Project ;
           eurio:title ?title .
  OPTIONAL { ?project eurio:startDate ?startDate . }
  OPTIONAL { ?project eurio:endDate ?endDate . }
  OPTIONAL { ?project eurio:identifier ?identifier . }
}
ORDER BY ?startDate ?title
LIMIT 100
```

2. Top 25 projects by number of linked publications

PREFIX eurio: <http://data.europa.eu/s66#>

```
SELECT ?project ?title (COUNT(DISTINCT ?work) AS ?pubCount)
WHERE {
  ?project a eurio:Project ;
           eurio:title ?title ;
           eurio:identifier ?id .

  SERVICE <http://localhost:3030/thiago/sparql> {
    ?work eurio:identifier ?id .
  }
}
```

```
GROUP BY ?project ?title
ORDER BY DESC(?pubCount) ?title
LIMIT 25
```

3. Publications for a specific project + author names from OpenCitations (external dataset)

```
PREFIX eurio: <http://data.europa.eu/s66#>
PREFIX prism: <http://prismstandard.org/namespaces/basic/2.0/>
PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>
PREFIX literal: <http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/>
PREFIX pro: <http://purl.org/spar/pro/>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
```

```
SELECT DISTINCT ?given_name ?family_name ?doi
WHERE {
  <https://www.nwo.nl/projecten/nwa116018238> eurio:identifier ?id .
```

```
  SERVICE <http://localhost:3030/thiago/sparql> {
    ?work eurio:identifier ?id ;
        prism:doi ?doi .
  }
```

```
  SERVICE <https://sparql.opencitations.net/meta> {
    ?identifier literal:hasLiteralValue ?doi .
    ?br datacite:hasIdentifier ?identifier .

    ?br pro:isDocumentContextFor ?authorRole .
    ?authorRole pro:withRole pro:author ;
        pro:isHeldBy ?author_uri .

    ?author_uri foaf:givenName ?given_name ;
        foaf:familyName ?family_name .
  }
}
ORDER BY ?family_name ?given_name
```